

Environmental cost accounting and firm value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria

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Abstract

Past research on the relationship between environmental cost accounting and firm value has not provided clear conclusions, largely because of a focus on environmental cost accounting itself. It is necessary to move away from simply disclosing environmental accounting variables and instead focus on disclosing the elements of environmental cost accounting. This study examined the different cost components involved in environmental cost accounting. The research involved gathering data from the annual reports, environmental impact assessments, environmental and social mitigation plan reviews, environmental audit reports, and sustainability reports of manufacturing companies listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group as of December 31, 2023. This data covers an 11-year period from 2012 to 2022. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis. The research discovered that environmental prevention costs have a significant negative impact on firm value, while environmental remediation costs have a significant positive impact. Environmental waste management costs have a positive but insignificant impact on firm value. It was determined that the lack of expenditure on certain environmental costs, such as prevention, remediation, and waste management, can affect firm value. Manufacturing firms in Nigeria are advised to implement sustainable policies to encourage their involvement in environmental initiatives. The study suggests maintaining environmental prevention costs as they play a significant role in explaining changes in firm value, and recommends focusing more on environmental remediation and waste management costs.

Keywords: Environmental cost accounting, environmental prevention cost, environmental remediation cost, environmental waste management cost, firm value

Introduction

In developed countries such as the USA, Canada, and the UK, addressing environmental hazards caused by business activities has become a priority (Pacini & Attafuah-Wadee, 2022) ^[29]. Measures have been implemented to mitigate these hazards, including encouraging businesses to take responsibility for their environmental impact and implementing environmental remediation programs. Similar concerns about environmental issues are also present in developing economies like Ghana, South Africa, and Nigeria, as highlighted by researchers such as Dian *et al.* (2019) ^[8] and Ofoegbu and Megbuluba (2016) ^[26].

In Nigeria, there are significant environmental hazards caused by the manufacturing industry due to poor remediation policies, inadequate waste management of chemicals, and the release of dangerous materials into the environment. Stakeholders such as the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement

Agency (NESREA) and the Environmental Health Council of Nigeria (EHCON) have recommended that environmental regulators require manufacturing industries to be accountable for their actions (Adegbe, *et al.*, 2021) ^[1]. The Federal Government of Nigeria has started investigating environmental issues caused by industries in the country, but there has been a lack of emphasis on implementing efficient and consistent standards aligned with the sustainable development goals (SDGs) (Ezeagba, *et al.*, 2017) ^[14].

Literature suggests that the extent of environmental disclosures by firms can have a positive impact on firm value, as shown in studies by Damieibi (2023) ^[7] and Igbekoyi *et al.* (2021) ^[18]. However, Kolawole *et al.* (2023) ^[21], Olaoye and Alao (2023) ^[27], and Emeka *et al.* (2019) ^[11] found conflicting results, indicating a negative relationship between environmental accounting disclosure and firm performance. The varying results in previous studies suggest

that the topic of environmental accounting remains inconclusive. Research has primarily focused on the disclosure aspects of environmental accounting, as seen in studies by Oyedokun *et al.* (2019) [28], Uniamikogbo and Ali (2021) [32], Emmanuel (2021) [12], and Chude *et al.* (2022) [6], while the financial implications have been less explored.

Previous studies have focused on disclosure when examining firms' environmental practices. However, there is a need to shift towards analyzing the cost components of these practices to assess their impact on firm value. By exploring the potential influence of costs, companies may be motivated to enhance their environmental compliance. This study addressed this gap by examining the cost components of environmental accounting.

The broad objective of this study is to investigate how environmental costs impact the firm value of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Specifically, it analyzed the effects of environmental prevention costs, environmental remediation costs, and waste management costs on firm value.

This research will assist policymakers in assessing the financial impact of environmental accounting elements. By investigating the costs involved in environmental accounting, a more comprehensive understanding of the concepts will be gained, surpassing previous studies that concentrated on disclosure aspects. This will offer stakeholders a more thorough assessment of environmental accounting in Nigerian manufacturing companies.

Other sections of the study covers literature review which explains how the study variables were conceptualized, the theoretical foundations of the study, and a review of empirical data. The third section describes the data and methods used to meet the study goals, including the research design and criteria for selecting the sample size. The fourth section includes the data analysis and a discussion of the results, while the final section contains the conclusion, recommendations, and policy implications of the findings.

2. Literature review

2.1 Conceptual review

This study utilizes environmental prevention cost, environmental remediation cost, and environmental waste management cost as components of environmental cost accounting and their impact on firm value. This approach aims to offer a more detailed understanding of these concepts and how they relate to each other.

2.1.1 Firm value

Firm value has been defined in various ways. Oyedokun, *et al.* (2019) [28] characterize it as the assets held by a firm and the overall worth of the firm's owners. Companies that are effectively managed typically experience an increase in value, which is influenced by stakeholders' perception and public reputation, a minimal level of information disparity, enhanced profitability, and decreased capital expenses, which are ensured by environmental awareness (Sabrin, *et al.*, 2016) [30].

Tobin's Q, also known as the market-to-book value ratio, is a metric used to evaluate a company's worth by considering internal and external market factors. Created by Professor James Tobin in 1967, this ratio is unique in its comprehensive analysis of various company dynamics. The market-to-book value ratio, or Tobin's Q ratio, is calculated

by dividing the market price of the company's stock plus debt by the value of its assets (Igbino, 2021) [19]. In this study, Tobin's Q is utilized to assess firm value by taking into account both internal company dynamics and external market assessment.

2.1.2 Environmental cost accounting

Environmental Cost Accounting (ECA) involves tracking the expenses related to a company's environmental impact, such as waste disposal. This includes costs for prevention, remediation, and waste management. Companies may face fines, penalties, or reputational damage for poor environmental practices. ECA is an extension of traditional cost accounting, focusing on the costs and effects of environmental impact. It assigns the costs of environmental impact to the responsible entities. Environmental accounting measures and reports on the use of environmental resources, costs of mitigating impact, and benefits for stakeholders (Mayndarto & Augustine, 2021) [22].

2.1.3 Environmental cost accounting and firm value

Environmental cost accounting is a component of environmental management accounting that focuses on recognizing and re-categorizing environmental impacts and costs to facilitate improved decision-making (Muhammed, 2018) [24].

Environmental cost accounting involves incorporating measures of natural resources and assessing the impact of organizational activities on them. This includes tracking energy consumption, solid and toxic waste production, water and air quality, and adherence to environmental regulations (Ezejiofor, *et al.*, 2016) [15]. The costs associated with environmental issues stem from resource use, pollution, and efforts to protect the environment (Ezeagba, *et al.*, 2017) [14]. Both local and international standards, such as those set by the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) and Global Reporting Initiatives (GRI), support the practice of accounting for environmental costs (Taiwo & Owolabi, 2019) [31]. Companies are now evaluated based not only on profitability, but also on their handling of environmental concerns, as the focus shifts towards the overall value of the firm (Falope, *et al.*, 2019) [16].

2.1.2.1 Environmental prevention cost and firm value

Communities near Nigerian manufacturing plants are highly concerned about the presence of harmful substances in their environment, which can negatively impact their health. There is a growing call for greater transparency regarding environmental conditions to ensure a higher quality of life and address broader societal issues. The environmental prevention costs primarily focus on expenses related to maintaining the health and safety of employees and community members, as well as the disclosure of these costs in reports (Mayndarto & Augustine, 2021) [22].

Environmental prevention cost is a vital component of accounting that produces reports for internal use in making management decisions regarding overhead, capital budgeting, and pricing, as well as for external use in sharing environmental information with the government, public, and financial community (Duque-Grisales, & Aguilera-Caracuel, 2019) [9]. Various pollutants resulting from

business activities are taken into account, including toxic, hazardous, and greenhouse gases. Both corporate managers and environmental advocates view environmental prevention cost as essential for enhancing environmental decision-making within organizations.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between environmental prevention cost and firm value of Quoted Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria

2.1.2.2 Environmental remediation cost and firm value

Green restoration or environmental remediation refers to the process of removing pollutants or toxins from water and soil. This is done to protect human health, ensure the well-being of businesses, and restore the environment.

According to Enahoro (2019) ^[13], environmental restoration involves helping the environment recover from damage through various methods like remediation and rehabilitation, with the goal of increasing a firm's market value. Imoobe and Iroro (2019) ^[20] note that stakeholders may not fully appreciate the benefits of restoration until they experience them firsthand. There are differing opinions on the impact of green regulations aimed at restoration on health, with neoclassical views suggesting negative effects on business despite social benefits. However, modern perspectives suggest that well-designed regulations can actually enhance business value and health by promoting innovation and attracting investors (Mayndarto & Agustine, 2021) ^[22].

H₀₂: No significant relationship exist between environmental remediation cost and firm value of Quoted Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria

2.1.2.3 Environmental Waste Management Cost and Firm Value

It is well known that waste is inevitable in the operations and production of any economy. The Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA) states that waste is a part of economic activities at home, in business, and in government, contributing to economic activity through resource recovery Akinlo and Iredele (2014) ^[2]. Waste management involves following the waste hierarchy of reduce, reuse, and recycle to maintain a clean environment and promote a healthy society. Waste reduction can be achieved by minimizing material inputs to products with high waste potential, categorizing waste, and utilizing modern waste processing facilities Miradha, *et al.* (2017) ^[23]. Waste reuse involves using waste as resources for the same or different purposes. A company's waste management strategy reflects its commitment to eco-efficiency, which can influence consumer demand for environmentally friendly products that use fewer resources and produce less waste and pollution (Mayndarto & Agustine, 2021) ^[22].

H₀₃: Environmental waste management cost does not significantly affect firm value of Quoted Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria

2.2 Theoretical review

2.2.1 Stakeholder theory

The stakeholder theory, created by Edward Freeman in

1984, focuses on how a company's actions can impact individuals and groups affected by their decisions (Mayndarto & Agustine, 2021) ^[22]. The theory argues that businesses should prioritize creating value for all stakeholders, not just shareholders.

The theory discussed in this study is relevant due to its focus on the environment, society, and shareholders. The study aims to demonstrate how firms can balance their social and environmental activities while meeting the goals of their owners. This theory has been utilized in various areas such as sustainability reporting, corporate social responsibility, audit, and internal control. In the context of Nigeria, where regulations on environmental cost accounting disclosure are lacking, this theory holds particular importance. This study is based on the stakeholder theory.

2.3 Empirical review

In Damieibi's (2023) ^[7] research, the impact of environmental accounting practices on the net profit of publicly traded oil and gas companies in Nigeria was examined. Environmental accounting practices such as pollution cost accounting, waste management cost accounting, and drainage cost accounting were utilized to represent environmental accounting. The study analyzed the annual audited financial reports of Nigerian oil and gas companies over a period of ten years (2012-2021). The hypotheses were tested using multiple regression analysis with ordinary least square estimation. It was noted that while the study did not include data from 2022, it is possible that the results may have differed if this additional year had been included. This study was an improvement on Damieibi's (2023) ^[7] work as it included data from 2022.

Another study conducted by Kolawole, *et al.* (2023) ^[21] found that environmental accounting has become increasingly important in response to the negative impact of environmental degradation. The study noted a focus on the manufacturing sector while neglecting the aviation industry. This research aimed to explore how environmental accounting practices affect the financial performance of Nigerian aviation firms, specifically examining their environmental research and development, pollution control policies, and waste management. The study used an ex-post facto research design and included the five aviation firms listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group as of December 31, 2021. Data was collected from annual reports spanning from 2016 to 2021, and analyzed using descriptive statistics and Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression analysis. The study suggested that Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS) should have been used instead of OLS to address data outliers, enhancing the analysis compared to previous research by Kolawole, *et al.* (2023) ^[21].

Olaoye and Alao (2023) ^[27] conducted a study on the impact of green accounting practices on the financial health of oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The study focused on the proprietary ratio and earnings per share as indicators of business health. The research design used was ex-post facto, aiming to provide unbiased information on the topic. The study employed a positivist philosophical approach and examined financial performance in relation to the adoption of green accounting practices. However, it was noted that a positivist approach alone may not fully capture the complex behavior of environmental accounting practices, as external

factors like stakeholder expectations and sustainability pressures can influence outcomes. The study suggests that incorporating stakeholder and sustainability theory can provide a more comprehensive understanding of environmental accounting practices and their impact on firm value. This study builds upon previous research by Olaoye and Alao (2023) ^[27] by incorporating stakeholder and sustainability theory.

Another interesting study conducted by Emeka-Nwokeyi and Osisioma (2019) ^[11] focused on examining the impact of sustainability and ethical disclosure components (social, environmental, and governance) on the market value of selected non-financial firms in Nigeria from 2006 to 2015. The researchers used content analysis to extract relevant disclosure data and firm market value information from the annual reports of the chosen firms. The analysis was conducted using pool ordinary least square (OLS) regression technique. It was noted that the study by Emeka-Nwokeyi and Osisioma (2019) ^[11] could have provided different results if data up to 2018 had been included in the analysis, as sustainability and disclosure data were available for the non-financial firms.

Chude, *et al.* (2022) ^[6] conducted a study on the impact of green accounting practices on the returns on assets and returns on equity of consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria, with the research rooted in stakeholder theory. The study utilized an ex post facto research design and included twenty-one consumer goods companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange in its final sample. Data from annual financial reports spanning from 2011 to 2017 were collected from secondary sources and analyzed using least squares regression in E-views 9. It is recommended to use the updated version of the statistical program due to potential internal errors that may have been resolved. The study by Chude, *et al.* (2022) ^[6] utilized E-views 9, an outdated version with generative problems, while the current study used E-views 12 for regression analysis.

The research conducted by Uniamikogbo and Ali (2021) ^[32] found that environmental accounting disclosure significantly impacts the share price, return on assets, and return on equity of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. It was anticipated that the study would analyze the specific components of environmental accounting disclosure that affect financial performance, but this information was not provided. The current study builds upon Uniamikogbo and Ali (2021) ^[32] by examining the disaggregated components of environmental cost accounting.

In a more detailed research project, Igbekoyi, *et al.* (2021) ^[18] examined the relationship between environmental accounting disclosure and financial performance among multinational companies listed in Nigeria. The study began by evaluating the companies' compliance levels and then investigated how environmental disclosure impacted financial performance, particularly in light of ongoing environmental issues in the Nigerian business sector due to the lack of a legal framework for sustainability reporting. The researchers analyzed data from the companies' annual reports spanning from 2011 to 2020, including measures such as the Environmental disclosure index, return on assets, and earnings per share, using descriptive statistics and panel regression analysis. The study also discussed the debate surrounding the financial performance of

multinational companies before and after the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). While Igbekoyi, *et al.* (2021) ^[18] did not conduct a pre-post analysis, this current study improved upon their research by starting data collection from 2012, which marked the beginning of IFRS adoption in Nigeria.

Oyedokun *et al.* (2019) ^[28] examined how environmental accounting disclosure impacts the firm value of industrial goods companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The study utilized a sample of fifteen companies from 2007 to 2016, using data from audited annual reports. The researchers did not provide a rationale for ending data collection in 2016 when data was available until 2018. It is suggested that the results of the study may have differed if data up to 2018 had been included. This current study builds upon Oyedokun *et al.* (2019) ^[28] by extending data collection to include years up to 2022.

The study by Cheska, *et al.* (2022) ^[5] investigated the relationship between environmental accounting disclosure (EAD) and firm profitability and value. The research focused on thirty publicly-listed chemical, mining, and oil companies in the Petrochemical Industry in the Philippines, known for their contribution to pollution. The study used a causal-explanatory research approach and collected financial and environmental data from 2015-2019 from annual reports and corporate governance reports. EAD was assessed using the EAD Index, while profitability was measured by Return on Assets, Return on Equity, Net Profit Margin, and Debt to Equity Ratio, and firm value was evaluated using Tobin's Q. It is noted that the findings may have varied if data beyond 2019 were included.

Emmanuel (2021) ^[12] conducted a study on green accounting disclosure and its impact on the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study focused on the effects of green accounting disclosure on the ROA, ROE, and share price of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Data was collected from the annual reports of forty out of the sixty-six manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as of December 31, 2019, covering the period from 2010 to 2019. Descriptive statistics and panel regression methods were used for data analysis. The study employed the Arellano and Bond (1991) GMM estimator to address potential endogeneity issues, although this estimator was considered outdated for a 2021 study. The research improved upon Emmanuel (2021) ^[12] by using the Dynamic Ordinary Least Square of Eviews released in 2023 for data analysis.

Akpan and Simeon (2021) ^[3] investigated the impact of sustainability disclosures on the cash flow return on investment of shareholders in oil and gas companies in Nigeria. They utilized secondary data and employed an ex post facto research design. The study conducted time series and cross-sectional analyses on selected oil and gas firms listed on the Nigeria Stock Exchange as of December 31, 2020, over a seven-year period from 2014 to 2020. Content analysis methods were used to gather data on sustainability parameters. Unlike Akpan and Simeon (2021) ^[3], who did not thoroughly address environmental sustainability practices, this study focused on key environmental costs and sustainability variables including environmental prevention, remediation, and waste management costs.

Huang and Fu (2022) ^[17] examined how the adoption of

environmental accounting impacts the financial performance of companies in Taiwan. They analyzed data from annual reports of 32 companies listed on the Taiwan stock exchange using ANOVA. The results indicated a positive correlation between environmental accounting and financial performance. It is suggested that future studies should consider using regression analysis, specifically Dynamic Ordinary Least Square (DOLS), for a more accurate analysis of continuous data. This study builds upon the research of Huang and Fu (2022) [17] by incorporating regression analysis.

2.4 Gap in literature

From the literatures reviewed, there exist a conceptual gap. Past studies have focused majorly on the concept of disclosure and not the cost element. The cost element of environmental accounting is crucial to any organization as it affects its firm value.

Previous studies have yielded mixed results. Uniamikogbo and Ali (2021) [32] and Kolawole (2023) [21] reported positive results, whereas Huang and Fu (2022) [17], Olaoye and Alao (2023) [27], and Chude, *et al.* (2022) [6] reported negative results. The current study also noted that there is a lack of research on the year 2022. Most studies have focused on the oil and gas industry, non-financial industry, multinational companies, and aviation industry rather than the manufacturing industry, as evidenced by Igbekoyi, *et al.* (2021) [18], Damieibi (2023) [7], Oyedokun, *et al.* (2019) [28], Huang and Fu (2022) [17], Olaoye and Alao (2023) [27], and Chude, *et al.* (2022) [6].

Some unique gaps in the reviewed studies include the use of the positivism approach, Ordinary Least Square (OLS) for regression analysis, an outdated 1991 GMM Estimator in a study conducted in 2021, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for continuous data analysis, aggregation of environmental accounting variables, the use of Eviews 9 for analysis, and exploration of sustainability concepts outside the study's original scope. The study extends its scope up to 2022, which sets it apart from previous research. While some studies have examined environmental cost accounting and

its impact on firm value in Nigeria, particularly in manufacturing companies focusing on return on assets and return on equity, there is limited research on Tobin's Q.

Based on the identified gaps, this study updated the scope to 2022 and considers the disaggregated environmental cost accounting proxies such as the environmental prevention cost, environmental remediation cost and environmental waste management cost, Tobin's Q to proxy firm value and focus on the manufacturing sector, employ the use of the Panel Least Square (PLS) as a better update of the OLS instead of ANOVA and focus on a multiple regression rather than a single regression analysis. This study, also employed the use of the current Eviews 2023 for the regression analysis and 2012 formed the basis for data to capture the effect of IFRSs adoption in Nigeria.

3. Materilas and Methods

The study utilized a longitudinal research design to analyze the potential effects of changes in independent variables on the dependent variable. The population of the study included all publicly traded manufacturing companies on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) from 2012 to 2022, with 2012 being selected due to the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in Nigeria. Data for the manufacturing companies were only available up to 2022. Fourteen manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) were purposefully selected for this study based on specific criteria. These criteria include being among Nigeria's top thirty capitalized companies according to the Society for Corporate Governance Nigeria (2017; 2023), being listed on NGX from 2012 to 2022, and having accessible annual reports and other environmental reports on their websites. These reports contain information on environmental costs and sustainable plans. The companies chosen are leaders in the sector based on their market capitalization. Data on environmental prevention cost, environmental remediation cost, environmental waste management cost, and Tobin's Q were extracted from the published reports on the companies' websites.

Table 1: Sample Determination Table

S/n	Manufacturing Firms by Sector	Populatio n	*Sample Selection Criteria (2012-2022)	Environmental Cost Accounting Variables			Sample Size
				EPC	ERC	EWC	
*Sample Selection Criteria: (i). Top 2 Capitalized Manufacturing Firms, (ii). Manufacturing Firms that have their environmental prevention cost, environmental remediation cost and environmental waste management cost reports from 2012 – 2022 in the annual reports, environmental impact assessment (EIA) report, environmental and social mitigation plan review (ESMPR), environmental audit report (EAR) and sustainability report (SR).							
1.	Agriculture	5	✓	2 out of 5 firms	2 out of 5 firms	2 out of 5 firms	*2
2.	Conglomerates	6	x	-	-	-	-
3.	Construction/Real Estate	9	x	-	-	-	-
4.	Consumer Goods	21	✓	2 out of 21 firms	2 out of 21 firms	2 out of 21 firms	*2
5.	Healthcare	7	✓	2 out of 7 firms	2 out of 7 firms	2 out of 7 firms	*2
6.	ICT	8	✓	2 out of 8 firms	2 out of 8 firms	2 out of 8 firms	*2
7.	Industrial Goods	13	✓	2 out of 13 firms	2 out of 13 firms	2 out of 13 firms	*2
8.	Natural Resources	4	✓	2 out of 4 firms	2 out of 4 firms	2 out of 4 firms	*2
9.	Oil and Gas	9	✓	2 out of 9 firms	2 out of 9 firms	2 out of 9 firms	*2
	Total	76					14

Source: Author's Compilation, 2024

Notes: EPC = Environmental Prevention Cost

ERC = Environmental Remediation Cost

EWC = Environmental Waste Management Cost

3.1 Model Specification

The model used in this study was adapted from the model of Amaegbu & Onyali (2021) [4], given as follow: $ROI_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 EPC_{i,t} + \beta_2 EDC_{i,t} + \beta_3 EMEC_{i,t} + \mu_{i,t} + \dots + a$

Where: ROI is return on asset, EPC is Environmental Prevention Cost, EDC is Environmental Education Cost, and EMEC is Environmental Management and Education Cost.

This study improves on Amaegbu & Onyali (2021) [4] model by considering the effect of a control variable on the model and the model lack a control variable. It is believed that firms are of different sizes and ignoring to control the effect of the sizes in a model can give a robust results. This study adapts Amaegbu & Onyali (2021) [4] model by making the dependent variable Tobin's q and adding a control variable, thus we have:

$FV = f(ECA) \dots \dots \dots b$
 $FV = f(EPC, ERC, EWC) \dots \dots \dots c$

$FV_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 EPC_{i,t} + \beta_2 ERC_{i,t} + \beta_3 EWC_{i,t} + \beta_4 FMS_{i,t} + e_{i,t} \dots d$

Where,
 FV = Firm Value
 EPC = Environmental Prevention Cost
 ERC = Environmental Remediation Cost
 EWC = Environmental Waste Management Cost
 FMZ = Firm Size

α = Constant; i = of a particular firm; t = Time Series; β_1 - β_3 , = Regression of the Independent Variable; e = Error Term. The apriori expectation of this study is that $EPC > 0$, $ERC > 0$, $EWC > 0$, i.e. the coefficient of the independent variable β_1 , β_2 , and $\beta_3 > 0$. The data collected for the research was analyzed using the Panel Least Square (PLS) for the regression analysis of the econometric statistical package "STATA 14". The descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and the unit root diagnostic tests was carried out on the data to determine its appropriateness, checking for robustness.

Table 2: Measurement of Variables

Variables	Description	Measurement	Sources
Dependent Variable Firm Value			
Tobin's Q (Dependent Variable)	This is the market-to-book value ratio of a firm.	It is measured by dividing the market price of the company's stock plus debt by the value of its total assets Total cost spent on environmental prevention-related projects as stated in Directors' report Total cost spent on repairs of environmental damage-related projects as stated in the Directors' report. Total cost spent on environmental waste management-related projects as stated in Directors' report. Total amount relating to assets (current and non-current) as stated in the statement of financial position.	Igbinovia, (2021) [19] and Cheska, <i>et al.</i> (2022) [5]. Amaegbu & Onyali (2021) [4]. Enahoro (2019) [13] and Igbinovia, (2021) [19]. Amaegbu & Onyali (2021) [4] and Miradha <i>et al.</i> (2017) [23]. Effendi (2021) [10] and Akpan Nkanta (2021) [3].
Independent Variable Environmental Cost Accounting			
Environmental Prevention Cost (Independent Variable) Environmental Remediation Cost (Independent Variable) Environmental Waste Management Cost (Independent Variable)	This is the cost expended to prevent environmental degradation and hazards Environmental remediation cost is a cost incurred in the process of assisting the recovery of the environment from degradation. This is a cost expended on to ensure a clean environment and a healthy society.	Total amount relating to assets (current and non-current) as stated in the statement of financial position.	Effendi (2021) [10] and Akpan and Nkanta (2021) [3].
Control Variable Firm Size	This represents the total assets of the firm.		

Source: Author's Compilation, 2024

4. Results and Discussion of findings

4.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 3 presents descriptive statistics that describe the interaction of the data, including the mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values for both outcome and explanatory variables. The study considers important elements such as minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, sum, skewness, and kurtosis for the variables used. Tobin's (TBQ) has an average of .3477 with a standard deviation of .5545, indicating high variation in firm value among the sampled firms. The coefficient of variation is 1.59456, suggesting over 100 percent variation from the mean. The minimum TBQ value is -.7969671 and the maximum is 1.328624, representing the range for the manufacturing industry. The total Tobin's q value is 42.08369, with TBQ being

negatively skewed and normally peaked at -.1843784 and 2.399874 respectively. The normality test yielded a figure of 2.366425 and a probability value of 0.306293, indicating a normal distribution. EPC has an average value of -.0266928 and a standard deviation of .7392694, suggesting high variation in firm value among the sampled companies. The coefficient variation is -27.69547, indicating over 100 percent variation. The range of EPC values is from -.9995562 to .999639, with a total sum of -3.229828. EPC is positively skewed and normally peaked at .1330843 and 1.430321. The normality test showed a figure of 13.03605 and a probability value of 0.001477, suggesting an abnormal distribution.

Table 3 presents summary statistics for environmental remediation cost (ERC), with an average of -.1053503 and a standard deviation of .6789669, indicating a high variation

in firm value. The coefficient of variation is -6.44485, representing over 100 percent variation. This high variability in ERC compared to other variables in manufacturing companies is further illustrated by a minimum ERC value of -.9999737 and a maximum value of .9976887, with a total sum of -12.74739. ERC is positively skewed and normally peaked with values of .1349524 and 1.56098. A test for normality resulted in a figure of 10.96248 and a probability value of 0.004164. Similarly, Table 3 displays that the environmental waste management cost (EWC) has an average of .0420078 and a standard deviation of .6597438, indicating a significant variation in firm value among the sampled companies. The coefficient of variation is 15.70528, representing a variation of over 100 percent. This high variability in EWC compared to other variables in manufacturing companies is further demonstrated by a minimum value of -.9998878 and a maximum value of .9975085. The total sum of EWC for all companies is 5.08294. The data for environmental waste

cost is negatively skewed and normally distributed, with a skewness value of -.1655103 and a kurtosis value of 1.721404. A test for normality yields a value of 8.849595 and a probability value of 0.011977, indicating a normal distribution.

Table 3 displays the statistics for firm size (FS), indicating an average of 7.90186 and a standard deviation of .8767631, showcasing a high level of variation in firm value among the sampled firms. The coefficient of variation further supports this, with a value of .1109566, indicating over 100 percent variation. This suggests a moderate variability in firm size based on total assets, with a coefficient of variation of 11 percent. The minimum and maximum values for FS are 4.435247 and 9.370732 respectively, with a total sum of 956.125. Additionally, firm size is negatively skewed and abnormally peaked, with values of -.616395 and 3.578078. The normality test yielded a figure of 10.01264 and a probability value of 0.006695, suggesting a normal distribution.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	TQ	EPC	ERC	EWC	FS
Observations	121	121	121	121	121
Mean	.3477991	-.0266928	-.1053503	.0420078	7.90186
Std. Deviation	.5545866	.7392694	.6789669	.6597438	.8767631
Coeff. Variation	1.59456	-27.69547	-6.44485	15.70528	.1109566
Minimum	-.7969671	-.9995562	-.9999737	-.9998878	4.435247
Maximum	1.328624	.999639	.9976887	.9975085	9.370732
Sum	42.08369	-3.229828	-12.74739	5.08294	956.125
Skewness	-.1843784	.1330843	.1349524	-.1655103	-.616395
Kurtosis	2.399874	1.430321	1.56098	1.721404	3.578078
Jarque-Berra	2.366425	13.03605	10.96248	8.849595	10.01264
Probability	0.306293	0.001477	0.004164	0.011977	0.006695

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2024)

4.2 Test of variables

4.2.1 Correlation analysis

The study utilized the correlation coefficient to examine the linear connection between environmental protection cost (EPC) and firm value (FV) of publicly listed manufacturing companies. The coefficient was determined to be -0.1813 with a probability of 0.0466, indicating a negative correlation between EPC and FV. This suggests that a one-time increase in EPC would lead to an 18.13% decrease in firm value. On the other hand, the environmental remediation cost (ERC) was found to have a coefficient of 0.2147 and a probability of 0.0180, showing a positive and significant correlation with firm value. A one-time increase in ERC would result in a 21.47% increase in firm value. However, the relationship between environmental waste management cost (EWC) and firm value was deemed insignificant at 5%, with a coefficient value of 0.0950 and a probability value of 0.3002. This suggests that a one-time increase in EWC would lead to a 9.50% decrease in firm value. Additionally, a negative and significant correlation was observed between firm size and firm value, with a coefficient value of -0.1971 and a probability value of 0.0302.

Table 4 presents the statistical analysis of the relationship between environmental remediation cost (ERC), environmental protection cost (EPC), environmental waste management cost (EWC), and firm size (FSZ) for listed manufacturing firms. The results show a negative correlation between ERC and EPC with a coefficient value of -0.1077 and a probability value of 0.2396, indicating that the correlation is not significant. Similarly, there is a negative correlation between EWC and EPC, with a coefficient value of -0.0803 and a probability value of 0.3812. In contrast, a positive and insignificant correlation is found between FSZ and EPC, with a coefficient value of 0.0753 and a probability value of 0.4120. Additionally, a significant negative correlation is observed between EWC and ERC, with a coefficient value of -0.0161 and a probability value of 0.8606. On the other hand, a positive correlation between FSZ and ERC is deemed insignificant, with a coefficient value of 0.0031 and a probability value of 0.9728. Lastly, the relationship between FSZ and EWC shows a positive correlation, with a coefficient value of 0.0412 and a probability value of 0.6534, indicating an insignificant correlation between firm size and environmental waste management cost.

Table 4: Correlation Analysis of the Variables

	TOBINSQ	EPC	ERC	EWC	FSZ
TOBINSQ	1.0000				
EPC	-0.1813*	1.0000			
	0.0466				
ERC	0.2147*	-0.1077	1.0000		
	0.0180	0.2396			
EWC	0.0950	-0.0803	-0.0161	1.0000	
	0.3002	0.3812	.8606		
FSZ	-0.1971*	0.0753	0.0031	0.0412	1.0000
	0.0302	0.4120	0.9728	0.6534	

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2024)

4.2.2 Normality test

The Shapiro-Wilks test of normality was used to assess the normality of residuals, with the results displayed in Table 5. The value obtained was greater than 0.05 at a 5% significance level, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis that the data is normally distributed across the models. Therefore, it is concluded that the residuals of the models are not normally distributed.

Table 5: Shapiro-Wilk W Test for Data Normality

Variables	Obs	W	V	Z	Prob>z
Firm value residuals	121	0.98645	1.313	0.611	0.27076

Table 5b: Skewness/Kurtosis tests for Normality

Variables	Obs	Pr(Skewness)	Pr(Kurtosis)	adj chi2(2)	Prob>chi2
Firm value residuals	121	0.4445	0.5254	1.00	0.6051

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2024)

4.2.3 Multicollinearity Test

The data in Table 6 indicates that there is no issue of multicollinearity. This is supported by the fact that all variables have VIF values below 10 and tolerance values above 0.10, as per the standard guideline. As a result, the study can use regression coefficients to forecast the impact of independent variables on dependent variables with confidence, and the results can be deemed reliable.

Table 6: Tolerance and VIF Value

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
EPC	1.03	0.975415
ERC	1.01	0.987625
EWC	1.01	0.990653
FSZ	1.01	0.991931
Mean VIF	1.01	

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2024)

4.2.4 Test for heteroskedasticity and auto-correlation

The analysis in Table 7 indicates the presence of heteroscedasticity based on a probability value of 0.0049, lower than the expected threshold of 0.05, suggesting that the error term is consistent across the residuals. The auto correlation test also reveals significance at 5 percent with a probability value of 0.0024, indicating the presence of

autocorrelation. The cross-sectional dependence test in Table 7 strongly supports the null hypothesis of cross-sectional dependence, with a probability value of 0.0000 and an average absolute correlation of 0.328. This suggests that sustainability reporting and financial performance under random effect conditions exhibit cross-sectional dependence. Overall, the analysis points to issues of heteroscedasticity, autocorrelation, and cross-sectional dependence, which were addressed using panels corrected standard errors (PSCE).

Table 7: Test for Heteroskedasticity and Auto-Correlation

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity	
chi2(1) = 7.92	Prob > chi2 = 0.0049
Wooldridge test for autocorrelation	
F(1, 10) = 16.143	Prob > F = 0.0024
Pesaran's test of Cross Sectional Independence	
no cross-sectional dependence (P>0.05)	6.902, , Pr = 0.0000
Average absolute value of the off-diagonal elements = 0.328	

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2024)

4.2.5 Panel unit root test of the variables

The findings of the unit root tests are presented in Table 8, indicating that all variables are integrated at order zero (I(0)). Consequently, there is no need to conduct a co-integration test to establish the long-term relationship between the variables. The panel least squares method is able to accurately estimate a reliable model with minimal errors.

Table 8: Panel Unit Root Test

Variable	Levin-Lin-Chu unit-root test		Harris-Tzavalis unit-root test	
	Statistics	p-value	Statistics	p-value
TOBIN'SQ	-2.9206	0.0017	-2.9863	0.0014
EPC	-5.0250	0.0000	-9.6081	0.0000
ERC	-3.4151	0.0003	-10.8325	0.0000
EWC	-6.2429	0.0000	-12.2317	0.0000
FSZ	-3.0633	0.0011	-7.9687	0.0000

Source: Researcher’s Computations (2024)

4.2.6 Model Specification Test

The results of the Hausman specification test for the study objective are displayed in Table 9. The findings indicate that the p-value for the model interpretation of the three objectives is not statistically significant at a 5 percent level. This suggests that the variation across entities is assumed to be random and unrelated to the independent variables in the models. Therefore, the random-effect model is deemed the most appropriate for interpretation. Additionally, the Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test for random effects was performed to determine the superiority between pooled OLS and random effect models, with the results favoring the random effect model due to its statistically significant p-value at a 5 percent level.

Table 9: Regression Specification Test

Hausman Test: Ho: difference in coefficients not systematic			
chi2(3) = 2.00		Prob > chi2 = 0.7359	
Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test for random effects			
Var	sd =	sqrt(Var)	
Tobins Q	.3075663	.5545866	
e	.0972256	.3118102	
u	.0882367	.2970467	
Test: Var(u) =	0	chibar2(01) =	191.09
		Prob > chibar2 =	0.0000

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2024)

4.3 Environmental cost accounting and firm value

The study examined the impact of environmental cost measures on firm value in Nigeria, specifically looking at environmental prevention cost, detection cost, and remediation cost controlled by firm size. The results, displayed in Table 10 after conducting a Best Linear Unbias Estimate (BLUE), suggest that firm size affects firm value. The Hausman specification test yielded a p-value of 0.7359, indicating that the variation across entities is likely unsystematic, making the random-effect model most suitable for interpretation. Additionally, the Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test favored the pooled OLS regression over the random-effect model. Despite statistical issues such as heteroskedasticity, autocorrelation, and cross-sectional dependence, the researcher used correlated panels corrected standard errors regression to address these errors. The regression results showed statistical significance, with a Wald chi2 of 19.80 and a probability of 0.000, indicating that the model is statistically significant at 5%. The R-Squared value of 0.1272 suggests that the independent variables explain 12.72% of the variation in the dependent variable, with the remaining variables captured by the error term. Overall, the study concludes that environmental cost measures have a significant impact on the firm value of manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Table 10 indicates that the Coefficient of environmental prevention cost (EPC) did not meet the expected value of $EPC > 0$ in this study, with a negative coefficient of -0.1126806 and z-statistics of -1.99 . This result was significant at the 5% level, with a p-value of 0.047 , suggesting that the negative impact of environmental protection costs on firm value is statistically significant. Similarly, the Coefficient of environmental remediation cost (ERC) also did not align with the expected value of $ERC > 0$, having a positive coefficient of 0.1653087 and z-statistics of 2.29 , significant at the 5% level with a p-value of 0.022 . The analysis of environmental waste cost (EWC) showed a coefficient value of 0.1107293 , z-statistics of 1.43 , and an insignificant p-value of 0.154 , indicating that while waste management costs may demonstrate environmental responsibility, they do not significantly impact firm value. Additionally, the study found that firm size as a control variable had a negative effect on the firm value of the sampled manufacturing firms in Nigeria, with a coefficient value of -0.1181103 , z-statistics of -2.62 , and a significant p-value of 0.009 . This suggests that the size of manufacturing firms may influence their environmental costs, leading to negative consequences on their firm value. Some previous studies have shown similar results to Cheska

et al. (2022) ^[5] regarding the negative impact of environmental accounting disclosure on profitability or firm value. Additionally, the findings on environmental remediation costs align with Emmanuel's (2021) ^[12] research on the positive effects of environmental accounting disclosure on the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study's results are different from those of Damieibi (2023) ^[7], who stated that environmental accounting has a positive and significant impact on firm value. It also contradicts the findings of Igbekoyi *et al.* (2021) ^[18], which suggested that environmental management has a positive effect on firm value. Additionally, the study's results do not align with Akpan and Simeon's (2021) ^[3] research on the impact of environmental accounting practices on shareholders' value in Nigeria, which found a significant effect on shareholders' value. The study indicates that the level of environmental cost element significantly influences firm value.

Table 10: Panels Corrected Standard Errors Regression Analysis

Panel-corrected				
TobinsQ	Coef.	Std. Err.	Z	P> z
EPC	-.1126806	.0566031	-1.99	0.047
ERC	.1653087	.0720796	2.29	0.022
EWC	.1107293	.0776543	1.43	0.154
FSZ	-.1181103	.0450917	-2.62	0.009
_Cons	1.292757	.3350687	3.86	0.000
Number of obs = 121				
R-squared = 0.1272				
Wald chi2(4) = 19.80 Prob>chi2 = 0.0005				

Researcher’s Computation (2024)

4.4 Policy implication of findings

The study revealed that different environmental costs have varying effects on firm value, with environmental prevention costs having a negative impact, environmental remediation costs having a positive impact, and environmental waste management costs having a minimal impact. These findings suggest that manufacturing firms in Nigeria should pay attention to their environmental accounting practices as they can influence firm value. Understanding the impact of environmental costs on firm value can help management make informed decisions about how to allocate resources. Failing to invest in certain environmental costs may have either positive or negative consequences on firm value. It is recommended that manufacturing firms in Nigeria establish policies that promote active participation in environmental initiatives such as prevention, remediation, and waste management. Furthermore, Nigerian regulatory bodies such as NESREA, Federal and State Ministry of Health, and EHCON have the potential to increase compliance among Nigerian manufacturing firms by implementing policies that incentivize investment in environmental hazard prevention, remediation of environmental issues caused by business activities, and proper waste management.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The research investigated how environmental cost accounting impacts the value of companies. The findings revealed that environmental remediation and waste management costs have a positive and significant impact on

the firm value of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. On the other hand, environmental prevention costs were found to have a significant negative effect on firm value. These results align with previous studies that have shown a negative relationship between certain environmental accounting costs and firm value in Nigeria. Overall, the study concluded that disclosing environmental accounting costs plays a significant role in influencing firm value. This research adds to the existing knowledge by providing evidence of the impact of environmental cost accounting on the firm value of manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

According to the research results, it is suggested that manufacturing companies in Nigeria should continue to prioritize environmental prevention costs, as they play a significant role in affecting changes in firm value. Additionally, companies should focus on the costs associated with environmental remediation, as they directly impact firm value. The study also recommends that manufacturing companies in Nigeria should consider investing in waste management, as it has been shown to have a positive but insignificant influence on firm value.

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